

Perspectives of the ASHA Special Interest Groups

Motivating Adolescents to Participate in Literacy Intervention: A Case Example from Telepractice

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Purpose. Motivation declines as children reach adolescence. Poor motivation inhibits participation and engagement in language-based interventions. The purpose of this article is to demonstrate how intervention can be designed to increase client motivation to participate while improving language-based literacy skills.</p> <p>Method. Motivation and behavior change techniques (Teixeira, 2020) based on self-determination theory are presented, as are examples of how to integrate these techniques into contextualized language intervention with adolescent clients.</p> <p>Conclusion. Incorporating motivation and behavior change techniques into contextualized language interventions with adolescents promotes self-determination and motivation through satisfaction of their need for autonomy, relatedness, and competence while simultaneously addressing language-based literacy deficits.</p>
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Response to Editor and Reviewers:</p> <p>Thank you for your detailed comments and suggestions to improve this manuscript. I appreciate the time and effort the reviewers provided. Your feedback has helped me to significantly reduce the length of this paper. I have addressed the editor's and the reviewers' comments below:</p> <p>Per APA format, please check heading format and utilize et al. for three or more authors throughout.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •These changes have been addressed throughout this manuscript. <p>In lines 85-86, please rephrase this sentence so it reads more clearly, perhaps leading with "The core of this theory...."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •This sentence has been rephrased. <p>In line 109-111, please rephrase the sentence so it reads smoothly. Maybe changing the word "and" to "as well as" would facilitate that?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •This sentence has been rephrased. <p>In line 113, keep the third item in the list grammatically consistent with the first two. Or, the word "and" could be added in place of the comma after "settings."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •This sentence has been rephrased. <p>In line 168, please remove "his or her."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •This phrase has been removed <p>In line 308, I think the word "of" is missing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •This grammatical error has been fixed. <p>Comments from Reviewers:</p> <p>Reviewer 1:</p>

Is the information presented in this paper consistent with ASHA policies and positions?

Reviewer 1: Yes:

Does the author reference the most recent versions of ASHA position and policy statements?

Reviewer 1: No: Only 1 ASHA reference is cited, but the complete reference is not provided in the references list.

•This reference has been added to the reference list.

Reviewer 1 Comments to Author: As an ASHA ex officio, my review is focused on evaluating matters relating to ASHA policies or other forms of ASHA-endorsed guidance. This paper mentioned one ASHA resource on page 5 line 48 ["language-literacy intervention services declines substantially (ASHA, 2000)"] , but the reference is not included in the references list. Please provide the complete citation.

•This error has been fixed. It should have read (ASHA, 2018) and this reference has been added to the reference list.

Reviewer 3:

I did have some difficulty following the deeper discussion about SDT, motivation and intrinsic motivation. For example, line 76 "Essential to self determination theory, details regarding the barriers to and facilitators of it are reviewed in detail." Yet, the section that immediately follows this sentence is a discussion about SDT. From lines 97 to 146 were difficult to follow and may need to be revised to more clearly make specific points; I had difficulty understanding the author's points and predicting what would come next in the manuscript. From line 47 (97?)through line 121, the author appeared to be discussing intrinsic vs. extrinsic motivation and autonomy and motivation; some of this may not be needed and is perhaps a bit repetitious? Perhaps different and more specific subheadings would help, well as some reworking of the content. I recommend a subheading between lines 121 and 122 that tells the reader that what follows is more details about the continuum of motivation. The explanation that follows is a detailed discussion of the Deci & Ryan (2017) figure. Is this level of depth necessary with the terms that are included? Could this section be reworded and be more reader friendly?

•This section was reworked and shortened substantially. I omitted portions that were not directly relevant to SDT for SLPs. For example, I omitted Figure 1: The SDT Continuum of Motivation and the detailed description. I also removed Appendix A: Classification of Motivation and Behavior Change Techniques and instead recreated it as a table (Table 1) to make this section more reader-friendly. Additionally, I omitted the section under the heading "Threats to Client Self-Determination." I believe that substantially paring this section down has improved the readability of this portion of the manuscript.

The figures illustrate possible intervention activities and provide ideas/resources for clinicians to consider using. The tables also are helpful and provide a nice guide for readers to more clearly understand the rationale and ways in which contextualized language intervention connect with the motivating techniques discussed in the manuscript. I do wonder if Figure 1 (motivation continuum) could be simplified or explained differently. It was already clear to me as a reader that the justification for the described case example was to motivate intrinsically.

•After reading this comment, I was in agreement with Reviewer 3. The figure depicting the motivation continuum and the extensive description of the motivation continuum was not really necessary. Both have been removed.

Reviewer 3: This manuscript is comprehensive and contains rich clinical thinking. As a reader who is interested in applying the motivational strategies, I might feel a bit overwhelmed attempting to implement all of them. Therefore, would it be useful to include a few sentences that readers might consider implementing one or two in each of the three needs areas as a way to begin? Also, while the conclusions are highly readable and relate directly back to the content, is there a need for citations again?

•A sentence was added to the conclusion indicating that this tutorial serves as a guide for several ways in which motivation and behavior change techniques can be incorporated into SLPs' practices, although incorporating all of them immediately may be overwhelming. Additionally, after rereading the conclusion, it does not appear that additional citations are needed.

Reviewer 4:

The case example for applying motivational strategies is appreciated. Since the child

for this case is also from a marginalized population, it would be good to include any observations or topics seated within a culturally relevant context. For example, as part of ascertaining Dwayne's attitudes, how were cultural/familial attitudes integrated? How do these relate to his perception of reading and writing? This section would benefit from some editing to pare down details that might not be highly relevant to the intervention

- I agree that it is important to integrate cultural and familial attitudes. After rereading this section of the manuscript, I believe that this has been addressed. As noted in the case example, when Dwayne was attending school in person on the reservation, he was receiving needed support to assist him with his literacy deficits. Additionally, it states in the case example that Dwayne's mother reported that she wants to help Dwayne with his literacy skills, but is uncertain how to do so. Further, the client in this case example provides specific examples in which he wishes that his literacy skills were commensurate with that of his peers (e.g., texting with friends). Although not explicitly stated, I believe that this illustrates that the reservation school, the mother of the client, and the client himself value literacy.

It is suggested that this section be reframed within a strengths-based perspective. It is likely that Dwayne is being required to code-switch when relating narratives or utilizing vocabulary. For example, it may not be surprising that Dwayne is surprised that composers revise if that type of music composition is not part of his lived experience.

- I agree that it is extremely important to focus on clients' strengths and to take their culture and lived experiences into account when formulating goals. I would argue that this was done in this case example (which was largely based on an actual client). The SLP in this case example asked the client what he found important, and Dwayne indicated that he wanted to participate in the impromptu "rap battles" that occur among his friends and cousins at the annual powwow. This is a situation in which he is immersed in his primary culture. He wants to participate with his peers who are also members of that culture. Further, rap and hip hop music is extremely popular on (many) reservations, and there is even a subgenre known as "Native Hip Hop" or "Indigenous Hip Hop." For these reasons, I feel that this is part of Dwayne's lived experience.

Goal Selection and Intervention: The ensuing two section are lengthy and while Appendix 1 is helpful, it is confusing for the reader to toggle back and forth to reference the techniques listed. The paper is several pages over the limit – this section may be a place where material could be cut without losing the focus of the paper. Rather than presenting an entire therapy plan, it may be clearer to start with a broad area of motivation techniques (e.g, supporting autonomy) and provide an example of how one or two strategies within that technique (e.g., provide choice) were incorporated into the lesson.

- Appendix A has been omitted. The content from Appendix A has been recreated in Table 1. Several sentences from the therapy plan were deleted to decrease the amount of text while preserving the original intention of the paper- to illustrate how motivation and behavioral change techniques can be incorporated into contextualized language interventions.

Line Item Edits:

Reference is not provided in Table 1.

- This is now Table 2- Ukrainetz has been referenced.

Line 79: Give acronym SDT here.

- According to APA 7, beginning a sentence with an initialism should be avoided.

Overall: It will help the flow and clarity of the paper to use active voice when possible.

Examples:

Line 76: Suggest: Barriers and facilitators essential to self-determination theory....

- This has been changed.

Line 85: Suggest: The core of this theory.....

•This has been changed.

Line 87: Suggest rewording: Three basic psychological needs are essential....

•This has been changed.

MOTIVATING ADOLESCENTS TO PARTICIPATE IN LITERACY INTERVENTION

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4 Motivating Adolescents to Participate in Literacy Intervention: A Case Example from

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Telepractice

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Conflict of Interest

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19

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Abstract

Purpose. Motivation declines as children reach adolescence. Poor motivation inhibits participation and engagement in language-based interventions. The purpose of this article is to demonstrate how intervention can be designed to increase client motivation to participate while improving language-based literacy skills.

Method. Motivation and behavior change techniques (Teixeira, 2020) based on self-determination theory are presented, as are examples of how to integrate these techniques into contextualized language intervention with adolescent clients.

Conclusion. Incorporating motivation and behavior change techniques into contextualized language interventions with adolescents promotes self-determination and motivation through satisfaction of their need for autonomy, relatedness, and competence while simultaneously addressing language-based literacy deficits.

Keywords: adolescent, literacy, self-determination, motivation, telepractice

41 Students who demonstrate difficulty with literacy acquisition in the early elementary
42 grades often struggle to attain literacy proficiency in adolescence. Longitudinal studies of
43 children who exhibit difficulty with language and literacy attainment in the early elementary
44 school years show that these individuals frequently continue to experience difficulty in the
45 secondary school years (Catts et al., 2005; Lewis et al., 2015; Snowling et al., 2000; Young et
46 al., 2002). Yet as students with literacy deficits enter secondary school, the provision of needed
47 language-literacy intervention services declines substantially (ASHA, 2018) and is often
48 designed and delivered in a manner that is less than optimal (Ehren, 2002). Nippold (2010) noted
49 that the majority of public school-based speech-language pathologists (SLPs) work primarily
50 with children in the elementary grades rather than secondary grades, noting that often school
51 administrators, policy makers, and even some SLPs believe that it is too late to help adolescents
52 overcome their language disorders. One frequently cited barrier to success in adolescent literacy
53 interventions is poor engagement due to reduced motivation (Kamil et al., 2008; Manset-
54 Williamson & Nelson, 2005; O'Brien et al., 2007; Solis et al., 2014). Literacy engagement refers
55 to the time, effort, and persistence in literacy behaviors (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2000). Wigfield
56 and Guthrie (2010) describe engagement and motivation as existing in a spiral; when one rises or
57 drops, the other follows suit. Students who believe that reading and writing are too difficult will
58 often develop avoidance behaviors; they do not feel that they are competent, so do not try. That
59 is, their lack of motivation leads to disengagement.

60 Self-determination theory describes motivation as occurring on a qualitative continuum
61 with extrinsic motivation at one end and intrinsic motivation at the other (Ryan & Deci, 2000).
62 Extrinsic motivation refers to motivation that is primarily driven by some kind of external
63 pressure or reinforcement that is largely independent from the activity (e.g., reading or writing)

64 and is generally viewed as the least effective form of motivation. Intrinsic motivation refers to
65 the motivation one feels performing an activity for its own sake rather than from the desire for
66 some external reward and is viewed as the most effective form of motivation. Adolescents who
67 are intrinsically motivated to read or write do so for the enjoyment or sense of accomplishment
68 they experience. Intrinsic motivation plays a critical role in educational learning (Bye et al.,
69 2007; Richardson et al., 2012; Taylor et al., 2014) and promotes the use of deep processing
70 learning strategies (Rijavec et al., 2003) and higher academic engagement (Otis et al., 2005).
71 Despite its importance, a steady decline in students' intrinsic motivation as they progress from
72 lower to upper grade levels has been well documented (Bouffard et al., 2003; Corpus et al., 2009;
73 Gillet et al., 2012; Gottfried et al., 2001) with the greatest decline observed in struggling students
74 at approximately age 13 (Corpus et al., 2009; Gottfried et al., 2001). Following is a review of
75 self-determination theory and its influence on student motivation and learning.

76 **Self-Determination Theory**

77 Self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000) is a theory of human motivation,
78 emotion, and development focused on factors that either enable or hinder an individual's growth-
79 oriented processes. Self-determination theory (SDT) has proven efficacious in predicting
80 motivated behavior in multiple contexts and across various cultures (Chirkov & Ryan, 2001;
81 Oga-Baldwin et al., 2017; Sheldon et al., 2009; Yu et al., 2018) and is distinct from other
82 theories of motivation owing to its emphasis on *quality* of motivation rather than quantity
83 (Teixeira et al., 2020). Foundational to this theory is that motivation is a multidimensional
84 concept that varies in terms of quality and drives an individual's behavior. The three basic
85 psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are fundamental to SDT.
86 Autonomy involves a sense of initiative and ownership of one's actions. It is reinforced through

87 experiences of interest and value and challenged by experiences of being externally controlled,
88 either by rewards or punishments. Competence involves the feeling of mastery and the feeling
89 that one is capable of success. An individual's need for competence is gratified through the
90 provision of well-structured environments that offer challenges within one's zone of proximal
91 development (Vygotsky, 1978), positive feedback, and opportunities for growth. Relatedness
92 involves experiencing a sense of belonging and connection and is nurtured through respect and
93 caring.

94 According to SDT, these psychological needs must be met for individuals to feel
95 motivated to change and regulate their behaviors. When individuals engage in a behavior (e.g.,
96 reading, writing) for autonomous reasons, they feel that these actions were freely chosen and
97 aligned with their personal goals. Several studies have determined that students who were more
98 intrinsically motivated in educational settings demonstrated greater perseverance and
99 substantially lower rates of drop out than students who were not (Hardre & Reeve, 2003; Otis et
100 al., 2005; Ratelle et al., 2005; Vallerand et al., 1997). Numerous studies have also shown that
101 motivation that is self-determined is positively associated with greater academic achievement
102 (Guay et al., 2010; Hayenga & Corpus, 2010; Ratelle et al., 2007; Vansteenkiste et al., 2009) and
103 behavioral persistence (Ryan & Deci, 2017). Moreover, compared to students whose motivation
104 is not self-determined, students whose motivation is self-determined retain information with
105 greater facility, consolidate that information more readily (Vansteenkiste et al., 2009), and
106 demonstrate greater use of metacognitive strategies for language tasks (Vandergrift, 2005).
107 Further, students whose motivation was more self-determined indicated greater satisfaction in
108 educational settings, noted greater enjoyment in their schoolwork, and reported more positive
109 emotions in school (Black & Deci, 2000; Tian et al., 2014).

110 Conversely, when individuals feel compelled to engage in behaviors for reasons that
111 originate outside of themselves, they lack a sense of autonomy. Behaviors that are extrinsically
112 motivated are performed due to the positive or negative consequence to which that behavior is
113 connected rather than being performed out of interest (Ryan & Deci, 2000), such as reading a
114 certain number of books by the end of the school year to receive an reward or to avoid a
115 punishment. Further, such behaviors do little to support students' competence and relatedness.

116 **Factors that Support Self-Determination**

117 Some studies suggest that the decline of intrinsic motivation might be a result of
118 emerging extrinsic constraints and contingencies experienced by secondary school students
119 (Lepper et al., 2005). Learning becomes increasingly decontextualized and performance-oriented
120 after elementary school (Anderman et al., 1999). Eccles et al. (1993) noted that as students rotate
121 through different classrooms with different content-area teachers, students are given fewer
122 choices and more constraints are imposed upon them at a time when students' needs for
123 autonomy increase, thus undermining students' intrinsic motivation. However, the decline of
124 intrinsic motivation can be successfully mitigated by the degree to which students' psychological
125 need for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are met (Gnambs & Hanfstingl, 2016;
126 Stiglbauer, 2013). Teixeira et al. (2020) developed the *Classification of Motivation and Behavior*
127 *Change Techniques*, a classification system of the intervention techniques that satisfy these
128 psychological needs as the organizing principle. Although this classification system was
129 originally designed for behavioral interventions in healthcare settings, it can be applied to a
130 variety of behaviors, including the behaviors addressed in language-based literacy interventions
131 (e.g., decoding strategies, morphological analysis). What follows is a description of how SLPs

132 can promote intrinsic motivation through motivation and behavior change techniques (MBCTs)
133 using this conceptual framework (see Table 1).

134 {insert Table 1 about here}

135 **Autonomy.** Teixeira et al. (2020) noted seven MBCTs to support client autonomy. The
136 first involves elicitation and exploration of the client’s perspective on their condition (MBCT 1).
137 This collaborative exploration provides the SLP with the client’s perspective and gives the client
138 an opportunity to increase knowledge of their own difficulties. These insights help to inform the
139 SLP and client’s choices in intervention planning. The second (MBCT 2) involves prompt
140 identification of sources of pressure for behavior change. It is beneficial to know why the client
141 is engaging in literacy intervention; is there external pressure from a parent or teacher, or does
142 the adolescent wish to improve his or her reading or writing ability? This information will assist
143 the SLP in identifying any external or introjected regulation that may be at work and how that
144 may be impacting the adolescent. The next (MBCT 3) involves using non-controlling,
145 informational language. An SLP’s use of informational, non-judgmental language suggests to the
146 client that this is a collaborative rather than controlling process, and that he or she has some
147 freedom of choice in intervention. Using phrases like “*could* you try that?” instead of “*you*
148 *should* try that” shifts the locus of causality away from the SLP and toward the client. In the
149 exploration of aspirations and values (MBCT 4), the SLP guides the client in a discussion of
150 their aspirations, values, and interests, as well as an exploration of how changes in their
151 behaviors could be connected to them. By guiding the client to make these connections, the SLP
152 promotes autonomous self-regulation. Providing the client with a personally meaningful
153 rationale for behavior change (MBCT 5) can serve as the basis for the client’s development of
154 autonomous motivation. Another technique (MBCT 6) involves providing the client with

155 opportunities to make choices from a collaboratively developed list of behavioral options. For
156 example, options could include activities around which intervention will center or what aspects
157 of literacy will be targeted first. Providing choices promotes client input and ownership of
158 behavioral changes. Lastly, MBCT 7 involves encouraging the client to experiment and self-
159 initiate the targeted behavior. Encouraging clients to challenge themselves and engage in
160 independent experimentation with skill development promotes autonomous action through
161 intrinsic motivation.

162 **Relatedness.** Relatedness refers to the need to experience a sense of belonging and
163 connection and is addressed through the following MBCTs in Teixeira et al.'s (2020)
164 *Classification of Motivation and Behavior Change Techniques*. Acknowledging and valuing
165 client's perspectives and feelings (MBCT 8) shows the SLP's attention to and respect for the
166 client's point of view and fosters a warm and accepting therapeutic environment. The SLP
167 should also encourage the client to ask questions about their goals and progress (MBCT 9). By
168 doing so, the SLP helps to create a collaborative relationship that promotes trust. Another way to
169 demonstrate acceptance is to show unconditional positive regard (MBCT 10). When the SLP
170 demonstrates this, he or she conveys respect, care, and support regardless of whether the client
171 experiences success or failure during intervention sessions. Displaying a genuine interest in the
172 client (MBCT 11) shows him or her that the SLP truly values them and their input. This can be
173 done by inquiring about the client's thoughts, perceptions, personal history, and interests. The
174 SLP can demonstrate attentiveness to clients' responses through empathetic listening (MBCT
175 12). Empathetic listening promotes a trusting, collaborative, open, and respectful client-therapist
176 relationship. Providing opportunities for ongoing support (MBCT 13) is a means of
177 demonstrating care and personal involvement in the client. Lastly, should a client need additional

178 sources of support to facilitate desired behavioral change, such as a support group or peer group,
179 prompt identification of this need and connection to these sources (MBCT 13) can help the client
180 feel more confident to overcome potential challenges.

181 **Competence.** Competence refers to individuals' inherent desire to feel effective in
182 interacting with the environment (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Competence satisfaction encourages
183 individuals to adapt their behaviors to complex and changing environments, whereas competence
184 obstruction is likely to result in helplessness and decreased motivation. Addressing the obstacles
185 that may hinder behavioral change and exploring how the client might overcome them (MBCT
186 15) may result in increased confidence and reinforcement of existing skills. The SLP should
187 clarify expectations (MBCT 16) by providing well defined goals, a clear explanation of the
188 intervention process, and unambiguous expectations of outcomes. By this structure, the client is
189 less likely to experience future failure and perceive himself as incompetent. Additionally, the
190 SLP should assist in identifying goals that are meaningful to the client and are realistic, yet
191 challenging (MBCT 17), which also provides structure and minimizes future failure. Offering
192 constructive feedback that is explicit and specific (MBCT 18) provides the client with
193 encouragement and helps guide future behavior. Another way in which the SLP can help provide
194 structure, increase client confidence, and minimize future failure is to collaboratively develop an
195 explicit intervention plan (MBCT 19). A plan of action developed with the client supplies him
196 with a "roadmap" that will give him clear feedback about what he has achieved and the steps that
197 should be taken to continue to progress. Promoting prompt self-monitoring of progress (MBCT
198 20) reinforces self-awareness. Finally, exploring ways to deal with pressure that may undermine
199 competence (e.g., criticism from peers, negative feedback from a teacher) helps to increase
200 confidence and self-efficacy (MBCT 21).

201

Contextualized Language Intervention

202 Contextualized language intervention (CLI) is a term that has been used to describe an
203 approach to treatment in which specific linguistic skills are addressed within the context of an
204 authentic communication activity, such as writing an essay, preparing for a debate, or reading an
205 article (Ukrainetz, 2015). That is, rather than targeting an individual skill, such as decoding, in
206 isolation, the SLP approaches this skill in a whole-part fashion. First, the authentic
207 communication activity around which intervention will center is identified (i.e., the “whole”),
208 then the separate linguistic skills (i.e., the “parts”) needed to successfully engage in the
209 interaction are identified. Addressing the parts while keeping the whole as the end goal is
210 fundamental to CLI. Ukrainetz (2015) identified five components that are essential to
211 communication activities (see Table 2).

212

{Insert Table 2 about here}

213 A comparison of these components of a communication activity and the motivation and
214 behavior change techniques used in SDT-based interventions reveals several overlapping
215 qualities. Both emphasize the importance of organizing interventions around an activity that is
216 meaningful to the client (MBCT 6) and motivating the client to engage (MBCT 1-21). The
217 purpose of participating in the activity is a key principle (MBCT 5), as is a focus on the
218 conditions that either facilitate or constrain participation in the activity (MBCT 17). All of the
219 competence-supportive techniques (MBCT 15-21) address skills and strategies needed for
220 activity participation. Integration of MBCTs into CLIs requires little effort due to their inherent
221 similarities. What follows is a description of how motivation and behavior change techniques can
222 be incorporated into CLIs in a case example. This case is a hypothetical client whose profile is
223 likely very familiar to speech-language pathologists working with adolescents who struggle with

224 literacy skill development. Additionally, this client lives in the rural Mountain West region and
225 has been home-schooled since the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. The interventions in
226 this case example were presented via telepractice given the geographic distance between the
227 client and a physical clinic, the absence of school-based services, and the physical distancing
228 recommendations to decrease the spread of COVID-19.

229 **Case Example: Dwayne**

230 Dwayne, a 13-year-old Native American male, lives on a reservation where there are no
231 speech-language intervention services within several miles of his home. Dwayne had received
232 school-based language-literacy intervention from an itinerant SLP once weekly, but those
233 services were suspended during the pandemic. Dwayne had consistently struggled with the
234 literacy demands of the curriculum, and when his schooling moved to an online-only format, he
235 found it impossible to keep up with his studies. Seeing Dwayne's struggle and frustration, his
236 family opted to withdraw him from school and homeschool him but were uncertain how to help
237 him improve his reading and writing skills. They enrolled Dwayne in speech-language
238 intervention via telepractice through a private practice.

239 The SLP administered standardized assessments and discovered that Dwayne exhibited
240 significant difficulty with encoding, decoding, and overall writing ability, as well as mild deficits
241 in syntax use. However, these test results did not provide a complete picture of Dwayne's
242 strengths, weaknesses, and interests, nor did they reveal the language demands and pressures that
243 Dwayne regularly experiences. A CLI approach recommends assessing clients' motivation and
244 their comprehension of the purpose of school activities. Since Dwayne was being homeschooled,
245 the SLP asked his mother about the activities in which Dwayne was involved. His mother
246 reported that because Dwayne had had such a negative experience with attempting online

247 schooling, they were taking a break from schooling for a while. She further explained that
248 compared to the school he regularly attended where he knew all of his teachers and was provided
249 with extra supports, the online school experience left Dwayne feeling pressured to perform
250 exactly as his typically developing peers, feeling like no cared whether he understood the
251 lessons, and feeling generally incompetent. Dwayne’s mother also reported that Dwayne would
252 completely withdraw from communicating at the mere suggestion of reading or writing. She
253 mentioned that Dwayne was normally a very outgoing adolescent who was well known for his
254 sense of humor and playful personality. She indicated that she was very concerned that physical
255 distancing due to the pandemic and resultant isolation were having a significant negative impact
256 on Dwayne.

257 Dwayne’s experience with online schooling did not foster a sense of autonomy,
258 relatedness, or competence, leaving Dwayne completely amotivated to engage in any literacy
259 activities. Rather than focusing on curricular activities, the SLP shifted the primary focus of
260 intervention to supporting Dwayne’s psychological needs to enhance his intrinsic motivation. To
261 encourage Dwayne to feel accepted and respected, the SLP began by expressing an interest in
262 Dwayne’s hobbies, preferences, and personal history (MBCT 11). She was attentive to his
263 responses, allowing adequate time for him to express himself (MBCT 12) and acknowledged his
264 perspective when he described his struggles with literacy (MBCT 8).

265 Through this conversation, the SLP learned that Dwayne really missed seeing his friends
266 and cousins. He highly valued and had regularly attended social events like local high school
267 basketball games and track meets, as well as an annual powwow. When the SLP inquired about
268 communicating with his friends and cousins now, Dwayne explained that they preferred to text
269 each other in a group chat and indicated that communicating through phone calls was not “cool.”

270 Dwayne reported that he did not like texting because, “It goes too fast. As soon as someone
271 sends a message, another one comes in, and then another one. By the time I finish reading them,
272 the conversation has moved on.” He also explained that he makes lots of spelling errors when
273 drafting messages. He said his friends will sometimes tease him about these errors and that one
274 particularly bad error resulted in an argument because the recipient was insulted. Dwayne
275 reported that he usually just does not join in the text conversations anymore.

276 It was evident that Dwayne’s literacy deficits were negatively impacting his social life,
277 which appeared to further impede satisfaction of his psychological needs. This is not surprising
278 given that the most important transition period for social competence, including heightened self-
279 consciousness and increased value and complexity of peer relationships, occurs during
280 adolescence (Burns, 2020). The SLP recognized Dwayne’s need to engage with his peers as a
281 motivating factor to participate in literacy intervention. She engaged Dwayne in a discussion of
282 his values, interests, and goals and guided him in an exploration of how improving his literacy
283 skills could enhance attainment of those goals (MBCT 4). Dwayne expressed disappointment
284 that he was unable to attend last year’s powwow due to the pandemic, stating that he especially
285 missed the informal “rap battles” in which his friends routinely engaged when there. When the
286 SLP asked Dwayne if he was preparing a rap song for the upcoming powwow, he explained that
287 he would like to, but that he would not even know how to begin. Because this appeared highly
288 **motivating** for him, the SLP suggested that Dwayne set a goal for himself to compose the lyrics
289 for a rap song by the powwow. Dwayne enthusiastically agreed to this communication **activity**,
290 composition of a rap song, but demonstrated difficulty describing the **purpose** of doing so.
291 Initially, his comments were vague (e.g., “I don’t know. It’s fun. It’s cool, I guess”). The initial

292 step the SLP took was to present Dwayne with some lyrics of other songs for analysis, like this
293 excerpt (see Table 3) from *Kick, Push* (Fiasco, 2006).

294 {insert Table 3 about here}

295 After analyzing the lyrics together and following guided discussion, Dwayne noted that the
296 purpose of the song was to *tell a story*. After further discussion, Dwayne explained that the
297 singer was illustrating the obstacles he had to overcome (e.g., injury, angry neighbors,
298 prohibition from skateboarding) to become a good skater. He added that every pair of lines in the
299 lyrics ended in words that rhymed or nearly rhymed.

300 ***Activity Analysis***

301 The SLP employed dynamic assessment strategies to assess Dwayne's readiness to
302 engage in this activity. She asked Dwayne to try writing four lines of lyrics that ended in
303 rhyming words about a topic of his choice (MBCT 3). Dwayne recounted a personal story about
304 a time that he and his sister played a trick on their cousin and indicated that he would write about
305 that. His verbal recount of this personal narrative included adequate information and temporal
306 sequence, demonstrating sensitivity to listener needs. However, Dwayne struggled to complete
307 the writing. He did not develop an outline or any notes to guide his writing. Dwayne exhibited
308 significant difficulty spelling, and he could not readily identify if rhyming words that were
309 spelled using different orthographic patterns rhymed (e.g., *great* and *eight*). When he produced
310 two lines of text, one consisted of 6 syllables while the other consisted of 15. The SLP suggested
311 replacing some phrases with single words and restructuring the sentence to either lengthen one
312 line of text or shorten the other (e.g., *big* to *gargantuan*, *happening at the same time* to
313 *synchronous*). Dwayne exhibited difficulty identifying alternate vocabulary words to use and
314 struggled to rephrase his sentence so that the original meaning was retained while simultaneously

315 keeping the rhyming word in the sentence-final position unless he was given a moderate level of
316 scaffolding. Analysis revealed several **skills** and **strategies** needed for this activity. Because
317 Dwayne chose to compose lyrics about a personal narrative, discourse-level skills such as the
318 inclusion of story grammar elements and appropriate sequencing were needed. Additionally,
319 self-regulation strategies were needed to segment the overarching task (composing song lyrics)
320 into smaller, more manageable components (e.g., identifying rhyming words). Sentence-level
321 skills involving the reordering of syntactic components, such as center-embedding left-branching
322 clauses and passive voice constructions were frequently needed to preserve the line-final
323 positions of the rhyming words and to maintain a relatively consistent number of syllables in
324 each line of text, as were word-level skills, such as the ability to replace words or phrases with
325 synonyms. Phonological skills were needed to identify rhyming words, and orthographic skills
326 were needed for spelling. Further, fluent decoding was needed to recite the lyrics in time with the
327 accompanying music.

328 Weaknesses in Dwayne's underlying linguistic skills and his use of strategies were
329 revealed in this activity. Dwayne did not demonstrate any strategies for planning what would be
330 included in his lyrics, such as the main ideas or key words. Dwayne appeared to allocate all of
331 his working memory resources to encoding, leaving few resources available for composing the
332 complex sentences present in his oral language. Upon further discussion with Dwayne, it was
333 revealed that he purposely avoided many complex vocabulary words in his writing because he
334 did not know how to spell them, indicating that he did not have a strategy for learning the
335 orthographically correct spellings of those selected words. His attempts at spelling the more
336 complex vocabulary words revealed that Dwayne was not using his knowledge of morphemes
337 (i.e., the base words, word roots, and affixes) to inform his spelling. For example, when

338 attempting to spell *muscular*, Dwayne wrote *muskyelur*. The SLP informed Dwayne that
339 *muscular* is a word used to describe something that has to do with muscles as she typed *muscle*
340 on the shared screen. She prompted Dwayne to think of another way *muscular* might be spelled,
341 but he stated that he could not. Dwayne further explained that when reading rap lyrics aloud, one
342 has to read them pretty quickly; he feared that he would not be able to read “hard words” fast
343 enough to “stay on a beat.”

344 Analysis of this activity also revealed several **conditions** under which Dwayne was
345 working. Dwayne’s household consisted of a large, close-knit, extended family. Dwayne had a
346 particularly close relationship with his older sister, who was often present during his intervention
347 sessions although she was off camera. Dwayne was often distracted by the noise and activities in
348 the home requiring redirection to the intervention tasks. Dwayne was observed to advocate for
349 himself, asking others to lower their voices so he could pay attention, and his family members
350 were always quick to respond to his requests. It appeared that Dwayne was comfortable with his
351 family; he talked openly about his difficulty reading and writing, and his family members were
352 heard making supportive comments in the background. Dwayne mentioned that even though his
353 friends would sometimes tease him for his spelling and decoding errors, he felt that they did so
354 without malintent. He further explained that although he was looking forward to writing his own
355 rap lyrics and performing them for his family, he worried that if he did not read them fluently in
356 front of his friends, he would be subjected to more teasing. The immediate condition appeared
357 highly supportive, albeit somewhat chaotic, whereas the distant condition (i.e., rapping with his
358 friends at the powwow) was more competitive (MBCT 2).

359 *Goal Selection*

360 The SLP worked collaboratively with Dwayne to select the activity around which
361 intervention would focus, as well as to develop his language intervention goal and objectives
362 (MBCT 6). With guidance from the SLP, Dwayne recognized many of the skills and strategies
363 that needed to be addressed to improve his literacy abilities through participation in dynamic
364 assessment. Through both standardized assessment and informal, dynamic assessment, it was
365 evident that Dwayne exhibited no difficulty spelling words containing short vowel sounds
366 represented with common orthographic patterns; however, he achieved 0% accuracy spelling
367 words containing long vowel sounds (e.g., *man/mane, at/eight*). The SLP and Dwayne agreed
368 that one goal should be to increase his knowledge of the orthographic patterns used to represent
369 long vowel sounds. Short-term objectives, such as the following one, were developed to help
370 Dwayne meet this goal:

- 371 • Dwayne will independently spell 1- and 2-syllable words containing the following long A
372 spelling patterns with at least 90% accuracy over 2 consecutive sessions: *open syllable A,*
373 *A+ consonant+ silent E, AI, AY, EY, EA, EI, EIGH, ANG, and ANK.*

374 While the interventions were not focused on an activity from Dwayne's curriculum, this goal
375 was aligned with Common Core State Standards (CCSS, 2011), specifically CCSS.ELA-
376 Literacy.L.7.2.b. (Spell correctly).

377 Another goal was created to increase Dwayne's morphological awareness and semantic
378 knowledge to support his decoding, spelling, and comprehension of polymorphemic words and
379 homophonic words. One short-term objective to assist Dwayne in meeting this goal included:

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- 380 • To improve his morphological awareness and semantic knowledge, Dwayne will record
381 at least three sets of homophones per week in his word journal, including segmentation of
382 base words and affixes (when applicable) and student-friendly definitions.

383 This goal aligned with CCSS.ELA-LITERACY.L.7.4.B (Use common, grade-appropriate Greek
384 or Latin affixes and roots as clues to the meaning of a word) and CCSS.ELA-Literacy.RF.5.3.a
385 (Use combined knowledge of all letter-sound correspondences, syllabication patterns, and
386 morphology (e.g., roots and affixes) to read accurately unfamiliar multisyllabic words in context
387 and out of context).

388 A goal to address Dwayne’s difficulty writing complex sentences was also developed.
389 Because his difficulty appeared to stem from struggles to keep complex ideas in his working
390 memory long enough to transcribe them, objectives such as this one were addressed:

- 391 • Given a set of 2-3 simple, written, kernel sentences and a word bank of subordinate
392 conjunctions and relative pronouns, Dwayne will combine each set of kernel sentences
393 into a single sentence containing a subordinate clause with at least 90% accuracy.

394 This goal aligns with CCSS.ELA-Literacy.L.7.3.a (Choose language that expresses ideas
395 precisely and concisely, recognizing and eliminating wordiness and redundancy) and
396 CCSS.ELA-Literacy.L.7.1.c (Place phrases and clauses within a sentence, recognizing and
397 correcting misplaced and dangling modifiers).

398 In addition to the goals designed to improve Dwayne’s linguistic skills, a goal was also
399 included that targeted strategies to promote his self-regulation. While Dwayne’s executive
400 functioning skills appeared commensurate with that of his same-aged peers, he needed strategies
401 that facilitate planning and organization of written work so that he could divide this large task of

402 composition into smaller components. Strategies targeting self-regulation and revision were also
403 needed so that Dwayne could flexibly shift his focus from one aspect of writing (e.g., narrative
404 organization) to another (e.g., word choice). Some of the objectives designed to improve self-
405 regulation included:

- 406 • Dwayne will develop a plan for the iterative process of his composition in collaboration
407 with the SLP.
- 408 • Dwayne will utilize external supports (e.g., thesaurus, dictionary, word etymology
409 dictionary) during intervention sessions to aid in determining spelling, pronunciation, and
410 comprehension of words when needed without prompting.

411 This goal aligns with CCSS.ELA-LITERACY.L.7.4.C (Consult general and specialized
412 reference materials (e.g., dictionaries, glossaries, thesauruses), both print and digital, to find the
413 pronunciation of a word or determine or clarify its precise meaning or its part of speech) and
414 CCSS.ELA-Literacy.WHST.6-8.10 (Write routinely over extended time frames (time for
415 reflection and revision) and shorter time frames (a single sitting or a day or two) for a range of
416 discipline-specific tasks, purposes, and audiences).

417 Now that an activity was collaboratively selected and goals for intervention were
418 developed based on an analysis of the linguistic skills needed to engage in that activity, Dwayne
419 and the SLP were ready to develop an implementation plan. The SLP helped Dwayne organize a
420 plan to address his areas of deficit (i.e., the “parts”) while maintaining a focus on the lyric
421 composition project (i.e., the “whole”). Additionally, to support Dwayne’s social communication
422 with peers, she provided opportunities for him to use the products of his literacy skill
423 development exercises in communication exchanges with them.

424 *Developing the Plan*

425 The first step in this contextualized language-based literacy intervention was to clarify
426 expectations (MBCT 16) and help Dwayne develop a concrete plan of action (MBCT 19). The
427 SLP began by explaining that this activity would involve an iterative process that would occur
428 across multiple sessions. She noted that there were several individual linguistic skills that
429 Dwayne needed to practice to improve his writing. She told Dwayne to expect to revise and edit
430 his writing many times before he was finished. She further explained that she would help
431 Dwayne to first develop a plan for completing this activity. The SLP reminded Dwayne that he
432 had told her that the purpose of the selected activity was to *tell a story* and prompted him to think
433 of a personally relevant story he would like to tell (MBCT 6). Dwayne mentioned that his friends
434 would probably be pretty surprised to see that he had dyed the hair on one side of his head pink
435 and decided to write about that.

436 **Self-Regulation Strategies.** Dwayne benefitted from explicit instruction in how to develop a
437 plan to compose his lyrics and how to use external supports, such as dictionaries, thesauruses,
438 and even a word etymology dictionary. He also benefitted from instruction in how to use many
439 of the software features available in Microsoft Word (e.g., spell check, grammar check,
440 thesaurus, text-to-speech, etc.). Dwayne appeared genuinely surprised to learn that composers
441 seldom write an entire song in a single sitting and that multiple revisions were commonplace.
442 Dwayne was directed to develop a plan for composing his lyrics that included various steps in
443 the process and opportunities to self-monitor and self-evaluate. The SLP guided him through
444 plan development using non-judgmental language (MBCT 3) and specific, constructive feedback
445 regarding areas of linguistic weakness that he should plan to which he should devote additional
446 time (MBCT18). Dwayne developed a plan in collaboration with the SLP that included the

447 following steps. First, he was to select a personal story to tell. Dwayne would then identify the
448 key points in the story and put them in order in an outline. Next, he would select key words from
449 the story (and check the spelling of those words). Dwayne would then create lists of words that
450 rhyme with the key words (checking the spelling and ensuring that they did rhyme). After
451 creating the word lists, Dwayne was to then write pairs of sentences/lines that end in rhyming
452 words. Dwayne would count the number of syllables in each line of text, and if the number
453 differed by greater than two syllables, he would lengthen one line of text or shorten the other.
454 Dwayne would do this by rephrasing the sentences or by changing a word(s) in the sentence.
455 Finally, Dwayne would proofread his lyrics to determine if the lyrics made sense, all essential
456 components of the story were included and presented in sequential order, all words were spelled
457 correctly, and each pair of lines rhyme.

458 The SLP explained to Dwayne that he should expect to occasionally go back and revisit
459 another step. For example, when writing rhyming lines of text, he may discover that he needs to
460 create a few more lists of rhyming words. Although this plan was rather simple, it helped
461 Dwayne develop a clear plan of action (MBCT 19), clarify expectations (MBCT 16), and address
462 obstacles (MBCT 15), which help promote a sense of competence. The SLP explained that this
463 outline he created preserved the content of his story and the sequence of events and provided him
464 with the visual support needed to “offload” the amount of information that he would need to hold
465 in his working memory while focusing on specific aspects (e.g., syntax, spelling, vocabulary) of
466 his writing. Next, the focus of intervention would alternate between addressing selected
467 linguistic skills and application of those linguistic skills to composition of his song lyrics. The
468 SLP also shared that she was going to introduce strategies to help Dwayne monitor his own

469 behaviors and progress. Once Dwayne was pleased with his composition, the SLP indicated that
470 she would help him create an audio recording of his rap song.

471 By developing a plan *with* Dwayne instead of *for* him, the SLP utilized several
472 therapeutic techniques that supported his sense of autonomy and competence. Rather than taking
473 complete control of the intervention activity, she provided Dwayne with opportunities to make
474 choices (MBCT 6). Although the SLP suggested composing lyrics, she gave Dwayne the
475 opportunity to reject that idea and suggest another. Dwayne selected the topic of the song lyrics
476 and chose to use an outline rather than a graphic organizer. The SLP also provided Dwayne with
477 a meaningful rationale for the course that intervention would take (MBCT 5). Further, in
478 developing a clear plan of action (MBCT 19) and an expectation that Dwayne would gradually
479 take on more responsibility monitoring his own behaviors (MBCT 20), she provided him with a
480 predictable structure within which to operate and prepared him to become more self-aware.

481 *Alternating between the Parts and the Whole*

482 Intervention initially focused on the discourse-level activity of composition. After
483 Dwayne recounted his personal narrative, the SLP asked him what he found the most essential
484 components of his story to be. Using a shared electronic document and given a little assistance
485 from the SLP, Dwayne typed each component like so:

- 486 • *I was bored and wanted a new look*
- 487 • *I decided to dye my hair*
- 488 • *I bought pink dye*
- 489 • *My sister told me I can't put pink on my dark hair, she had to bleach it first*
- 490 • *I didn't believe her at first- I hoped she knew what she was doing*

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- 491 • *She was all ready to bleach my hair and I stopped her at the last second and said to only*
492 *do half*
- 493 • *I didn't know it would smell so bad and it burned. I didn't think I was going to make it*
- 494 • *I wanted to stop after that but she talked me into putting on the pink dye*
- 495 • *I was glad I did it but I went through a lot*

496 Now that the essential components of Dwayne's story (i.e., "the whole") were preserved, the
497 SLP prepared him to shift his focus to the linguistic skills he needed to improve (i.e., "the parts")
498 before returning to his composition. She initiated this transition by providing Dwayne with
499 immediate, specific feedback regarding the noted difficulties with spelling he demonstrated when
500 typing his outline (MBCT 18). She informed Dwayne that there are many rules governing
501 spelling patterns that he was probably never explicitly taught or had forgotten. She also
502 explained that were he to improve his spelling fluency, he would not need to rely so heavily on
503 corrective software features (e.g., spell-check, word prediction, auto correct), particularly since
504 they often resulted in his selecting an orthographically similar, but unintended word (MBCT 3).
505 The SLP further noted that Dwayne often omitted obligatory words (e.g., he typed sentences
506 without a verb) when typing that he did not omit when speaking. She explained that these are
507 common errors that everyone makes occasionally and are usually due to not having enough
508 "headspace" to focus on two things (i.e., spelling *and* grammar) simultaneously (MBCT 5).
509 When she asked what Dwayne thought about learning ways in which he could improve his
510 spelling, he agreed that this would be helpful for him (MBCT 1).

511 This exchange illustrates an important step in intervening with adolescents that differs
512 from how intervention is frequently carried out with younger clients. When intervening with
513 young children, SLPs do not necessarily ask permission or inquire about their thoughts regarding

514 the course of treatment. Younger children are more accustomed to unquestioningly following an
515 adult's lead and will often participate given extrinsic motivators, such as stickers or intermittent
516 breaks to play a game. By adolescence, clients' acceptance of the intervention plan and
517 willingness to participate becomes crucial for success in treatment. In this example, the SLP
518 supported the client's sense of relatedness by demonstrating interest in and curiosity about
519 Dwayne's personal history and life events that he found meaningful. She supported his sense of
520 autonomy by using non-controlling, non-judgmental language to discuss the difficulties she
521 observed Dwayne experiencing. By offering clear, specific feedback about those difficulties, she
522 provided information to help guide his future behaviors and encouragement that change was
523 possible, thereby fostering his sense of competence.

524 **Spelling.** The SLP explained that she was going to provide Dwayne with explicit
525 instruction in orthographic patterns and multiple opportunities to practice them with guided
526 support to improve his spelling (for detailed procedures, see Bear et al., 2016; Masterson &
527 Crede, 1999). Although Dwayne demonstrated a genuine interest in learning about the various
528 orthographic patterns used to represent the different long vowel sounds, he indicated that he
529 wished that he could learn them faster so he could participate in group texts with his friends. The
530 SLP listened to Dwayne's concerns empathetically and summarized them in a reflective
531 statement to ensure that she understood them correctly (MBCT 12). She then prompted Dwayne
532 to identify the barriers he felt were preventing his participation (MBCT 15). Dwayne indicated
533 that he was substantially slower reading others' texts and responding in a timely fashion. The
534 SLP again summarized his concerns in a reflective statement emphasizing the word *responding*
535 and asked if communication via text only involved responding (MBCT 12). Dwayne replied that
536 he could initiate a new text thread and, after a moment, added that he could take the time he

537 needed to prepare it and check it for errors before sending it. When the SLP probed further about
538 potential barriers that may be preventing Dwayne from participating in the group texts, he noted
539 that although he knew his friends were just engaging in good-natured ribbing when teasing him
540 about his errors, he still found it hurtful. The SLP encouraged Dwayne to explore some ways in
541 which he could respond to his friends when this happened. She asked Dwayne how he would
542 respond if his friends teased him about something else, like tripping on a shoelace. Dwayne
543 responded that he would “laugh it off” or make a joke about it himself. The SLP asked Dwayne
544 if felt that he could do the same with spelling errors. After collaboratively discussing a few ideas,
545 Dwayne and the SLP decided to create jokes about spelling using an online meme generator
546 (e.g., <https://imgflip.com/memegenerator>). Figure 1 illustrates two memes he created after
547 participating in spelling exercises in which orthographic patterns used to represent long and short
548 vowels were contrasted.

549 {insert Figure 1 about here}

550 After scaffolding Dwayne’s creation of a few “spelling memes,” the SLP encouraged him to
551 experiment with creating some on his own (MBCT 7). Dwayne began to view his spelling errors
552 as opportunities for exploration rather than a source of embarrassment and would often begin a
553 telepractice session asking, “Do you want to see the meme I made?” Dwayne also mentioned that
554 he eventually began sharing these jokes he created with his friends while texting.

555 **Morphological Awareness and Semantic Knowledge.** Dwayne’s interest in words and
556 their morphology increased as he learned about various spelling patterns. This was observed
557 when Dwayne selected key words from his story (e.g., dye, burn, blonde, pink, hair) and created
558 lists of rhyming words for his rap lyrics with support from the SLP. As he reflected on these lists,

559 he noted that there were several homophones (or near homophones) and frequently commented
560 on different the orthographic patterns used to represent them (e.g., *pond* and *pawnd* in the list of
561 words rhyming with *blonde*). The SLP informed Dwayne that the meaning of the words
562 influences the spelling. She encouraged him to examine words for morphological units (e.g., was
563 a suffix responsible for the homophonic pairing, as in *prince/prints?*) and orthographic patterns
564 (e.g., was the long vowel sound represented with a vowel combination, as in *main*, or with a
565 silent E, as in *mane?*). As homophones such as these were encountered, Dwayne added them to
566 an electronic word journal, identified each morpheme in the words, and drafted a student-
567 friendly definition of each. Because Dwayne was highly engaged in the spelling activities that
568 involved the creation of memes and because these memes appeared to function as an excellent
569 mnemonic device facilitating his recall of orthographic patterns, the SLP suggested that they do
570 something similar with homophones. The SLP introduced Dwayne to a digital storyboard creator
571 (<https://www.storyboardthat.com/>) and demonstrated how he could create homophone comic
572 strips and asked if that is something that he would be interested in trying (see Figure 2). Dwayne
573 enthusiastically participated in this activity.

574 {insert Figure 2 about here }

575 In addition, Dwayne added morphologically complex words derived from Latin and Greek roots
576 to his digital journal. Each entry was organized around a specific word root and included at least
577 three words derived from that root (for detailed procedures, see Collins & Wolter, 2019; Meaux
578 et al., 2020; Wolter & Collins, 2017) and a comic strip to serve as a visual mnemonic. (see
579 Figure 3).

580 {insert Figure about 3 here }

581 These activities encouraged Dwayne to experiment with words and morphemes both during and
582 after intervention sessions, and his desire to create these comic strips helped buoy his willingness
583 to tackle tough words. Before participating in these activities, Dwayne was observed to
584 frequently avoid complex words in his writing, using simple, synonymous words he found easier
585 to spell instead. By providing Dwayne with a meaningful rationale for using specific
586 orthographic patterns when spelling specific words (MBCT 5) and by encouraging him to
587 experiment with adding entries to his word journal (MBCT 7), the SLP was providing him with
588 autonomy support. As Dwayne created new entries for his word journal and as he reflected on
589 previous entries with the SLP, monitored and commented on his own skill development (MBCT
590 20), which supported his sense of competence. Dwayne gradually began replacing avoidance
591 behaviors with approach behaviors and exploration.

592 **Syntax.** Sentence-level interventions were frequently paired with interventions targeting
593 orthographic rules. As mentioned previously, Dwayne selected key words from his narrative and
594 then created lists of words that rhymed with those key words using a variety of orthographic
595 patterns (e.g., *dye, cry, hi, die, guy, high*). Sentence combining exercises were introduced to help
596 Dwayne increase the length and complexity of his written sentences (for detailed procedures, see
597 Balthazar & Scott, 2015; Hebert et al., 2018)

598 The SLP would then type simple sets of sentences using the words like so:

- 599 • My sister is tall.
- 600 • My sister reached the box.
- 601 • The box contained hair dye.

602 The SLP then directed Dwayne's attention to the second sentence and modified it like so:

- 603 • My sister (who) _____ reached the box (that) _____.

604 Dwayne was instructed to type the pertinent information from the first and third sentences in the
605 spaces created. The SLP continued having Dwayne combine sentences in this way until it no
606 longer appeared challenging. She gradually decreased the amount of scaffolding by ceasing to
607 supply the relative pronouns (or subordinating conjunctions) and then providing no cues as to
608 where in the sentence a clause could be added, presenting Dwayne with an optimal level of
609 challenge (MBCT 17). This gradual fading of cues afforded Dwayne the structure needed to
610 comprehend and master the task, thereby bolstering his sense of competence.

611 The SLP followed a similar procedure when instructing Dwayne in forming passive
612 sentences from active sentences. She would present Dwayne with a sentence written in the active
613 voice and prompt him to first identify the subject of that sentence and then the object. Dwayne
614 was then instructed to reorganize the sentence so that the object of the sentence came before the
615 subject and told him that he would also need to alter the verb (e.g., change “*is*” to “*was verbed*
616 *by*”). Dwayne required very little scaffolding with passive voice formation; he easily reorganized
617 his sentences after minimal, explicit instruction in how to do so. Dwayne performed similarly
618 when moving phrases within given sentences. The SLP presented Dwayne with written sentences
619 containing adverbial phrases and prompted him to identify the phrase in the sentence that tells
620 the reader “when” (or *how*, *where*, or *why*) the action takes place. She would then instruct
621 Dwayne to change the sentence so that the “when phrase” was in the first position of the
622 sentence. For example, when presented with the sentence, “I scroll through Tik-Tok every
623 night,” Dwayne identified “every night” as the “when phrase.” He copied and pasted that phrase
624 on a new line, then copied and pasted “I scroll through Tik-Tok,” yielding the new sentence,
625 “Every night, I scroll through Tik-Tok.” Again, Dwayne required minimal scaffolding to

626 complete these phrase movement exercises, and the SLP increased the complexity of the task
627 first by increasing the length of the sentences until this exercise was no longer challenging. Next
628 the SLP instructed him change the order of the phrases in the sentence without prompting
629 Dwayne to isolate the adverbial phrase.

630 Dwayne required very little instruction or scaffolding before he demonstrated proficiency
631 with the presented sentence-level tasks. In fact, Dwayne was observed to make comments, such
632 as, “That’s it? That’s all I have to do? That’s easy,” suggesting that what he primarily needed
633 was explicit instruction in the steps in the task. Dwayne benefitted significantly from the
634 structure provided through clear expectations (MBCT 16), tasks that were optimally challenging
635 (MBCT 17), and a clear plan of action (MBCT 19), all of which supported his sense of
636 competence. Additionally, the SLP used kernel sentences in these exercises that were related to
637 Dwayne’s personal history to show that she valued his experiences and interests (MBCT 11) to
638 support his sense of relatedness.

639 **Back to the Whole.** The activity around which intervention was focused was revisited
640 once individual linguistic skills were targeted. Cycling between individual skills and the larger
641 activity of composition was facilitated by designing individual skill instruction activities that
642 were designed with the larger activity in mind. Dwayne had created lists of rhyming words when
643 orthographic patterns were targeted, he examined the morphological structures and meanings of
644 those words and others and experimented with syntactic structures using these words and phrases
645 from his outline. These discrete skill activities not only strengthened Dwayne’s individual
646 linguistic skills through repeated exposures and systematic support, they also generalized to
647 authentic writing activities. Through alternating between individual skills and actual
648 composition, Dwayne composed his rap song (see Table 4).

649

{insert Table 4 about here}

650 Dwayne practiced his rap lyrics and selected accompanying background music from an online
651 digital audio workstation (<https://www.soundtrap.com>). The SLP had introduced Dwayne to this
652 website at this start of this thematic unit and encouraged him to explore the options available on
653 his own. Doing so resulted in Dwayne storing his favorite beats and instrumental samples outside
654 of scheduled intervention time. This audio workstation allowed Dwayne to adjust the tempo of
655 the background music to his oral reading rate as well as record his voice over the music.
656 Although Dwayne had never expressed an interest in his oral reading rate, he was notably
657 interested in reading his lyrics aloud quickly enough to keep up with his selected background
658 music.

659 This composition project promoted Dwayne's intrinsic motivation by supporting his
660 sense of autonomy, relatedness, and competence in multiple ways. The individual skills that were
661 addressed benefitted him immediately by supporting his communication in social contexts (e.g.,
662 texting) and later in discourse-level composition. Even though Dwayne was taking a break from
663 regular schoolwork, the contextualized interventions designed to improve his literacy skills were
664 aligned with Common Core State Standards.

665

Conclusion

666 This case example illustrates how contextualized language-based literacy intervention
667 can be implemented via telepractice to promote adolescent clients' intrinsic motivation through
668 satisfaction of their need for autonomy, relatedness, and competence. Speech-language
669 pathologists working with adolescent clients should invest in meaningful conversations with
670 them. The time spent getting to know adolescent clients, their personal interests, their histories,

671 and their social and family lives is invaluable in the development of a collaborative relationship
672 in which they feel accepted and respected, thereby bolstering their sense of relatedness. Had the
673 SLP in this case example not engaged in meaningful conversations with Dwayne, it is unlikely
674 that she would have learned of his sense of loss and disappointment arising from isolation from
675 his friends. By learning about Dwayne's feelings, she created opportunities for him to engage
676 with his peers in the short term (e.g., texting) and long-term (e.g., participating in impromptu
677 "rap battles" with his friends at an annual powwow) while simultaneously addressing his
678 language-based literacy deficits.

679 Although adolescents are not yet adults, they have outgrown childhood, increasing the
680 importance for autonomy. This yearning for autonomy can be satisfied by involving them
681 throughout the therapeutic process. SLPs who avoid controlling language and supply meaningful
682 rationales for any behaviors they suggest clients perform are more likely to promote an internal
683 locus of control in their clients. Providing these clients with choices whenever possible and
684 encouraging them to experiment with the behaviors introduced in intervention promotes a sense
685 of responsibility, autonomous action, and intrinsic motivation.

686 Revealing the explicit structure of the intervention process by involving adolescent
687 clients in intervention planning helps to increase their confidence in their own abilities and
688 minimizes future failures. Interventions that provide clients with an optimal level of challenge
689 are more likely to promote a sense of competence. It is also beneficial to include instruction and
690 guidance to adolescents in self-monitoring to reinforce self-awareness and success.

691 Contextualized language intervention is an ideal therapeutic framework in which
692 motivation and behavior change techniques can be integrated. Incorporating these techniques

693 into interventions with adolescents promotes self-determination through satisfaction of their need
694 for autonomy, relatedness, and competence. Satisfaction of these psychological needs is critical
695 in that they are primary determinants of intrinsic motivation, and thus, positive therapeutic
696 outcomes. While including every motivation and behavioral change technique in every therapy
697 session with every client may be overwhelming, the case example included in this tutorial is
698 intended to serve as a guide for clinicians who wish to begin incorporating these techniques into
699 their practices. It should be noted that these interventions and techniques can be used inside and
700 outside of school settings, as well as in person or via telepractice. In fact, many of the
701 technological features available to the client and SLP working from a shared screen were
702 beneficial to the client's literacy development and engagement in intervention.

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705 this project.

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860

861 Figure 1

862 *Example Spelling Memes*

863 Figure 2

864 *Sample Journal Entry for Homophones*

865 Figure 3

866 *Sample Journal Entry for Polymorphemic Words Derived from “Graph”*

867

Create your own at [Storyboard That](#)

Pond = small lake

Pawned = pawn + -ed

pawn	-ed
To pawn something means to trade it for money. The pawnbroker holds on to it for a while so you can trade the money back for the thing you left.	Past tense

Create your own at [Storyboard That](#)

Hear = to listen

You hear with your ear.

Here = a place

There, where, and here all refer to places.

Create your own at [Storyboard That](#)

bio	graphy
<i>life</i>	<i>A writing or drawing</i>
A writing (book) about someone's life	
photo	graph
<i>light</i>	<i>To write or draw</i>
To draw with light	
auto	graph
<i>self</i>	<i>To write or draw</i>
To write your "self" (your own name)	

Table 1

Classification of Motivation and Behavior Change Techniques (Teixeira et al., 2020)

Techniques Supporting		
Autonomy	Relatedness	Competence
MBCT 1: Elicit client's perspectives on condition or behavior	MBCT 8: Acknowledge and respect perspectives and feelings	MBCT 15: Identify and address barriers to behavioral change
MBCT 2: Prompt identification of sources of pressure for behavior change	MBCT 9: Encourage the client to ask questions	MBCT 16: Clarify expectations
MBCT 3: Use non-controlling, informational language	MBCT 10: Show unconditional regard	MBCT 17: Assist the client in setting optimal challenge
MBCT 4: Explore life aspirations and values	MBCT 11: Demonstrate a genuine interest in the client	MBCT 18: Offer constructive, clear, and relevant feedback
MBCT 5: Provide a meaningful rationale	MBCT 12: Use empathetic listening	MBCT 19: Help the client develop a clear and concrete plan of action
MBCT 6: Provide choice	MBCT 13: Provide opportunities for ongoing support	MBCT 20: Promote self-monitoring
MBCT 7: Encourage the client to experiment with and initiate the behavior	MBCT 14: Prompt client to identify and seek sources of social support when needed	MBCT 21: Explore ways of dealing with pressure

Table 2

Essential Components of a Communication Activity (Ukrainetz, 2015)

Component	Definition
Activity	Purposeful event or task
Motive	The underlying force driving the client's engagement
Purpose	The reason for participating in the activity
Condition	The facilitating or constraining features of the immediate and broader contexts
Skill	Unconscious, automatic execution of actions or behaviors
Strategy	Conscious, deliberate execution of actions or behaviors

Table 3

Kick, Push Lyrics Excerpt

First got it when he was six,
didn't know any tricks

Matter of fact, first time he got on it, he slipped
Landed on his hip and busted his lip

For a week he had to talk with a lisp,
like this-s-s-s-s-s

Now we can end the story right here
But shorty didn't quit, it was something in the air

Yeah, he said it was something so appealing
He couldn't fight the feeling,

something about it
He knew he couldn't doubt it,

couldn't understand it, branded,
since the first kickflip he landed,

Labeled a misfit, a bandit
Ka-kunk, ka-kunk, ka-kunk; his neighbors couldn't stand it

So, he was banished to the park
Started in the morning, wouldn't stop 'til after dark,

When they said "It's getting late in here
So I'm sorry, young man, there's no skating here"

Table 4

Dwayne's Rap Lyrics

I was looking at Tik-Tok for the latest trends.
I wanted to do something to impress my friends.
I thought about changing my clothes or painting my toes.
I had even thought about piercing my nose.
But then I saw it. I knew I'd look so fly.
I ran to the store and bought a box of dye!
My sister said, "that color is out of reach.
To get your hair pink, we'll have to start with bleach."
Before she started, I said, "wait, just do half!"
Only a partial dye job? That made her laugh.
A towel around my neck and my hair pinned back,
"I hope she does it right, so my hair's not whack!"
The bleach was soaking in, so I held my towel tight.
And lo and behold, my black hair had turned white!
It took forever- my scalp began to burn!
The chemicals smelled; my stomach started to turn.
I was holding back tears, although I wanted to cry.
Girls go through this? I guess I'm glad I'm a guy!
My sister said, "Hold your head over the sink.
This is the last step, then your hair will be pink."
It wasn't easy. It caused me so much pain.
But in the end, I had a fabulous mane!
The moral of this story? To have great flair,
No pain no gain when it comes to your hair.

Response to Editor and Reviewers:

Thank you for your detailed comments and suggestions to improve this manuscript. I appreciate the time and effort the reviewers provided. Your feedback has helped me to significantly reduce the length of this paper. I have addressed the editor's and the reviewers' comments below:

Per APA format, please check heading format and utilize et al. for three or more authors throughout.

- These changes have been addressed throughout this manuscript.

In lines 85-86, please rephrase this sentence so it reads more clearly, perhaps leading with "The core of this theory...."

- This sentence has been rephrased.

In line 109-111, please rephrase the sentence so it reads smoothly. Maybe changing the word "and" to "as well as" would facilitate that?

- This sentence has been rephrased.

In line 113, keep the third item in the list grammatically consistent with the first two. Or, the word "and" could be added in place of the comma after "settings."

- This sentence has been rephrased.

In line 168, please remove "his or her."

- This phrase has been removed

In line 308, I think the word "of" is missing.

- This grammatical error has been fixed.

Comments from Reviewers:

Reviewer 1:

Is the information presented in this paper consistent with ASHA policies and positions?

Reviewer 1: Yes:

Does the author reference the most recent versions of ASHA position and policy statements?

Reviewer 1: No: Only 1 ASHA reference is cited, but the complete reference is not provided in the references list.

- This reference has been added to the reference list.

Reviewer 1 Comments to Author: As an ASHA ex officio, my review is focused on evaluating matters relating to ASHA policies or other forms of ASHA-endorsed guidance. This paper mentioned one ASHA resource on page 5 line 48 ["language-literacy intervention services declines substantially (ASHA, 2000)"] , but the reference is not included in the references list. Please provide the complete citation.

- This error has been fixed. It should have read (ASHA, 2018) and this reference has been added to the reference list.

Reviewer 3:

I did have some difficulty following the deeper discussion about SDT, motivation and intrinsic motivation. For example, line 76 "Essential to self determination theory, details regarding the barriers to and facilitators of it are reviewed in detail." Yet, the section that immediately follows this sentence is a discussion about SDT. From lines 97 to 146 were difficult to follow and may need to be revised to more clearly make specific points; I had difficulty understanding the author's points and predicting what would come next in the manuscript. From line 47 (97?)through line 121, the author appeared to be discussing intrinsic vs. extrinsic motivation and autonomy and motivation; some of this may not be needed and is perhaps a bit repetitious? Perhaps different and more specific subheadings would help, well as some reworking of the content. I recommend a subheading between lines 121 and 122 that tells the reader that what follows is more details about the continuum of motivation. The explanation that follows is a detailed discussion of the Deci & Ryan (2017) figure. Is this level of depth necessary with the terms that are included? Could this section be reworded and be more reader friendly?

- This section was reworked and shortened substantially. I omitted portions that were not directly relevant to SDT for SLPs. For example, I omitted Figure 1: The SDT Continuum of Motivation and the detailed description. I also removed Appendix A: Classification of Motivation and Behavior Change Techniques and instead recreated it as a table (Table 1) to make this section more reader-friendly. Additionally, I omitted the section under the heading "Threats to Client Self-Determination." I believe that substantially paring this section down has improved the readability of this portion of the manuscript.

The figures illustrate possible intervention activities and provide ideas/resources for clinicians to consider using. The tables also are helpful and provide a nice guide for readers to more clearly understand the rationale and ways in which contextualized language intervention connect with the motivating techniques discussed in the manuscript. I do wonder if Figure 1 (motivation continuum) could be simplified or explained differently. It was already clear to me as a reader that the justification for the described case example was to motivate intrinsically.

- After reading this comment, I was in agreement with Reviewer 3. The figure depicting the motivation continuum and the extensive description of the motivation continuum was not really necessary. Both have been removed.

Reviewer 3: This manuscript is comprehensive and contains rich clinical thinking. As a reader who is interested in applying the motivational strategies, I might feel a bit overwhelmed attempting to implement all of them. Therefore, would it be useful to include a few sentences that readers might consider implementing one or two in each of the three needs areas as a way to begin? Also, while the conclusions are highly readable and relate directly back to the content, is there a need for citations again?

- A sentence was added to the conclusion indicating that this tutorial serves as a guide for several ways in which motivation and behavior change techniques can be incorporated into SLPs' practices, although incorporating all of them immediately may be overwhelming. Additionally, after rereading the conclusion, it does not appear that additional citations are needed.

Reviewer 4:

The case example for applying motivational strategies is appreciated. Since the child for this case is also from a marginalized population, it would be good to include any observations or topics seated within a culturally relevant context. For example, as part of ascertaining Dwayne's attitudes, how were cultural/familial attitudes integrated? How do these relate to his perception of reading and writing? This section would benefit from some editing to pare down details that might not be highly relevant to the intervention

- I agree that it is important to integrate cultural and familial attitudes. After rereading this section of the manuscript, I believe that this has been addressed. As noted in the case example, when Dwayne was attending school in person on the reservation, he was receiving needed support to assist him with his literacy deficits. Additionally, it states in the case example that Dwayne's mother reported that she wants to help Dwayne with his literacy skills, but is uncertain how to do so. Further, the client in this case example provides specific examples in which he wishes that his literacy skills were commensurate with that of his peers (e.g., texting with friends). Although not explicitly stated, I believe that this illustrates that the reservation school, the mother of the client, and the client himself value literacy.

It is suggested that this section be reframed within a strengths-based perspective. It is likely that Dwayne is being required to code-switch when relating narratives or utilizing vocabulary. For example, it may not be surprising that Dwayne is surprised that composers revise if that type of music composition is not part of his lived experience.

- I agree that it is extremely important to focus on clients' strengths and to take their culture and lived experiences into account when formulating goals. I would argue that this was done in this case example (which was largely based on an actual client). The SLP in this case example asked the client what he found important, and Dwayne indicated that he wanted to participate in the impromptu "rap battles" that occur among his friends and cousins at the annual powwow. This is a situation in which he is immersed in his primary culture. He wants to participate with his peers who are also members of that culture. Further, rap and hip hop music is extremely popular on (many) reservations, and there is even a subgenre known as "Native Hip Hop" or "Indigenous Hip Hop." For these reasons, I feel that this is part of Dwayne's lived experience.

Goal Selection and Intervention: The ensuing two sections are lengthy and while Appendix 1 is helpful, it is confusing for the reader to toggle back and forth to reference the techniques listed. The paper is several pages over the limit – this section may be a place where material could be cut without losing the focus of the paper. Rather than presenting an entire therapy plan, it may be clearer to start with a broad area of motivation techniques (e.g., supporting autonomy) and provide an example of how one or two strategies within that technique (e.g., provide choice) were incorporated into the lesson.

- Appendix A has been omitted. The content from Appendix A has been recreated in Table 1. Several sentences from the therapy plan were deleted to decrease the amount of text while preserving the original intention of the paper- to illustrate how motivation and behavioral change techniques can be incorporated into contextualized language interventions.

Line Item Edits:

Reference is not provided in Table 1.

- This is now Table 2- Ukrainetz has been referenced.

Line 79: Give acronym SDT here.

- According to APA 7, beginning a sentence with an initialism should be avoided.

Overall: It will help the flow and clarity of the paper to use active voice when possible. Examples:

Line 76: Suggest: Barriers and facilitators essential to self-determination theory....

- This has been changed.

Line 85: Suggest: The core of this theory.....

- This has been changed.

Line 87: Suggest rewording: Three basic psychological needs are essential....

- This has been changed.

Learner Outcomes:

After reading this article, readers will be able to:

1. Identify the three psychological needs that need to be satisfied for individuals to feel motivated to change and regulate their behaviors according to self-determination theory.
2. Describe ways in which satisfying these psychological needs promotes clients' intrinsic motivation.
3. Apply motivation and behavior change techniques in their own interventions.